

The Influence of Weediness on Vegetation Seasonality Indicators: Examples from Romania

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20396140

Abstract: Temporally dense observations enable new ways to characterize land surface phenologies. Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs) are a rapid and flexible approach to marking key features of a dense time series of a vegetation index using nonparametric statistics. Here we explore how weediness within crop fields can affect VSIs and how the VSI framework could be tuned to detect weedy fields. We use Sentinel-2 time series of EVI2 over select fields in eastern Romania that we sampled in late June/early July of 2025. Results show variable influence of weediness on VSIs, depending on crop type, its seasonality, and landscape setting.

Keywords: crop seasonality; weediness; land surface phenologies; EVI2 time series.

1 Introduction

Within a NASA Land Cover Land Use Change project investigating the changes in agricultural land cover dynamics triggered by Romania's 2007 entry to the European Union, we developed a novel approach to characterize land surface phenologies (LSPs) of crops using dense time series. Prior approaches to LSP modeling that developed in an era of sparse observations relied on smoothing prior to the fitting to the parametric models from which phenometrics were derived. We use nonparametric statistics for rapid characterization of novel phenometrics we call vegetation seasonality indicators (VSIs). Here we compare VSIs from weedy fields of four crops with nearby fields of the same crop without weeds.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Remote Sensing Data

We calculated the VSIs for 2023 to 2025 using the ESA's Copernicus Sentinel-2 (S2A) product at 10 m (Drusch et al. 2012).

The Sentinel-2 Level-2A (L2A) product provides surface reflectance derived from observations acquired by the Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) onboard the Copernicus satellites Sentinel-2A (launched June 2015), Sentinel-2B (launched March 2017), and Sentinel-2C (launched September 2024). L2A products are generated through atmospheric correction of Level-1C top-of-atmosphere data using the Sen2Cor processor and are distributed in the Sentinel-2 tiling scheme based on the Military Grid

Reference System (MGRS) (Drusch et al. 2012). The dataset includes spectrally calibrated surface reflectance bands at 10 m, 20 m, and 60 m spatial resolutions and auxiliary layers such as the Scene Classification Layer (SCL). For this study, Sentinel-2 L2A tiles covering Romania (48 unique tiles) with cloud cover $\leq 50\%$ for the period 2023 to the end of 2025. We downloaded three bands—B04 (RED) and B08 (NIR), both at 10 m, and SCL at 20 m—directly from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) via OData interface (European Space Agency 2025).

2.2 Data preprocessing and Vegetation Index calculations

We calculated for each pixel the two-band Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI2) (Jiang et al. 2008) as shown in equation (1).

$$EVI2 = 2.5 \times \frac{(NIR-RED)}{(NIR+2.4 \times RED+1)} \quad (1)$$

For S2A, first the Scene Classification Layer (SCL) was resampled to 10 m to match the spatial resolution of the spectral bands, was used to mask out pixels labelled "Saturated or defective", "Cloud medium probability", "Cloud high probability", and "Snow or ice". We additionally masked out EVI2 values ($0.0 < x \leq 1.2$) because we focused on vegetated surface dynamics. All S2A images were then reprojected to the relevant Romanian projection: Pulkovo 1942 (58) / Stereo70 (EPSG:3844). To ensure pixel alignment during further raster merging, the error threshold for transformation approximation was set to 0 during reprojection using the GDAL library (GDAL/OGR contributors 2025).

To reduce noise in the EVI2 time series, we applied a three-step filtering procedure prior to VSIs calculations. The procedure addressed (i) duplicate acquisition dates, (ii) anomalously high-valued "spikes", and (iii) anomalously low-valued "troughs".

Because multiple observations may occur on the same calendar date (from overlapping satellite tiles), duplicate time stamps were consolidated by retaining only the maximum EVI2 value. We then removed isolated anomalous EVI2 spikes that were ecologically inconsistent with gradual vegetation growth, when the EVI2 value satisfied three conditions simultaneously. First, the observation exhibited a strong relative increase compared to the previous time step, exceeding an increase threshold

(50% of the previous value). Second, this increase was followed by a sharp decline exceeding a decrease threshold (30% of the previous value). Third, the EVI2 value recovered to a high value immediately after the drop. Finally, a sliding-window filter, a modified Best Index Slope Extraction (BISE) algorithm (Viovy et al. 1992), was applied to suppress sudden drops in the EVI2 time series. This filter evaluates whether a decrease represents a sustained seasonal transition or a transient fluctuation. For each observation, the magnitude of decrease relative to the last accepted value was assessed. If the decrease exceeded zero, subsequent observations were examined within a forward-looking temporal window of fixed length (two observations window). A proportional tolerance parameter (threshold of 25%) was used to determine whether the decline persisted. If the signal remained consistently low across the entire window, the decrease was considered persistent and retained as part of a genuine seasonal transition. If the signal recovered rapidly within the window, indicating a temporary disturbance or artefact, the observation was removed. These filtered EVI2 data were then used to calculate the Vegetation Seasonality Indicators.

2.3 Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs)

To capture the land surface phenologies of winter/spring crops, summer crops, and land cover types with perennial vegetation, we defined our annual observation window, which we designated as the “phenological year”, extending from November 1 through October 31 of the following year. Seasons within each phenological year were defined as follows: (1) “Spring” ran from November 1 through May 31, (2) “Summer” from June 1 through August 31, and (3) “Fall” from September 1 through October 31. The temporal timing of these seasonal windows was selected based on recently observed cropland dynamics in Romania. Part of the power of the VSI approach is the user’s flexibility in defining what periods constitute the seasonal windows to capture key dynamics in focal landscapes.

Next, to compose EVI2 values characteristic of the seasonal slices and the differences between these values, we extracted at each pixel the maximum EVI2 value within each season, and the median EVI2 value was calculated across all filtered observations in entire phenological year. In each case, we also recorded the date of observation corresponding to each seasonal EVI2 maximum.

Finally, differences between the three seasons were calculated, resulting in a total of ten VSI layers: (1) Annual median (AnMd), (2) Spring maximum (SpMx), (3) Summer maximum (SuMx), (4) Fall maximum (FaMx), (5) SpMx minus AnMd, (6) SuMx minus AnMd, (7) FaMx minus AnMd, (8) SuMx minus SpMx, (9) SuMx minus FaMx, and (10) SpMx minus FaMx. Note that the VSIs based on differences can assume negative or zero values, whereas the four core VSIs (viz., the three seasonal maxima and annual median) are always positive. Finally, note that VSIs can be calculated from other vegetation indices, but here we focus on VSIs from EVI2. Given space limitations, we focus here only on the three VSI seasonal maxima.

2.4 Linking ground observations to remotely sensed observations

During late June into early July 2025, we gathered georegistered digital photographs of fields and ancillary data (e.g., crop/cover type, weediness, view direction, and more) in six *județe* (counties) in eastern RO (754 samples) using a customized Esri’s ArcField Maps application. Back in the lab we manually adjusted the observation points from their nominal location at the edge of the field deeper into each field with no overlap between neighboring observations from the perspective of 10 m Sentinel-2 pixels. Each sample’s final location was agreed by two of us (GMH, MAT). To compare the crop fields that we observed and noted as “weedy” during the field

Figure 1. Four examples of VSI seasonal maxima of weedy fields compared to nearby fields with same crop type.

campaigns, we selected nearby field samples of the same cover type that were within a 900 m buffer. This selection resulted in weedy samples with a variable number of nearby non-weedy samples. We focus on major crops of Romania: wheat, rapeseed, sunflower, and maize.

Figure 2. Photos of weedy fields of (top to bottom) wheat, rapeseed, sunflower, and maize that are analyzed in Figure 1.

3 Results

Each panel in Figure 1 displays the seasonal maxima for a weedy crop field and some neighboring fields of the same crop type without apparent weedy infestations as observed during the 2025 field campaign. These three VSIs—SpMx, SuMx, and FaMx—are displayed from left to right. The x-axes indicate the dates the seasonal maxima were observed in each time series. Note that since these VSIs are derived from filtered time series, a seasonal maximum in a particular field may be later (e.g., wheat #3) or earlier (e.g., rapeseed #2) than in nearby fields.

Note that the x-axis scaling varies across the four panels of Figure 1, but the y-axis is scaled consistently across the panels. Weedy SpMx and SuMx appear higher in wheat but comparable for FaMx. In contrast, only SpMx appears higher in rapeseed but comparable for both SuMx and FaMx. The considerable variation in seasonal maxima across sunflower fields makes the VSIs of the weedy field

unremarkable. Note the sunflower panel includes a nearby field invaded by a perennial reed (*Phragmites* spp.), its seasonal maxima also fall within the spread of VSIs. The maize panel shows the weedy field to have higher SpMx but comparable SuMx and FaMx, although the latter is at the higher end of the spread.

4 Discussion

Samples shown in Figure 1 are few but illustrative. Figure 2 features photos of the selected weedy fields. Our analysis here just scratches the surface. There are several factors to consider in the broader issue of detectability of weedy fields with VSIs: (i) relative areal extent of weeds, (ii) relative stature of crops and weeds, (iii) relative phenologies, (iv) the lag between “start of growing season” and field preparation for planting of summer crops, (v) the lag between crop dry-down and harvest of winter/spring crops, (vi) agronomic practices, such as conservation tillage and application of pesticides, (vii) the field’s proximity to perennial wet areas harboring invasive species, e.g., *Phragmites* spp., (viii) the characteristics of the observing sensor, e.g., spatial, temporal, and spectral resolutions, and (ix) the temporal density of the filtered time series.

5 Conclusions

We have introduced, albeit briefly, the Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs), a new approach to characterize rapidly land surface phenologies using nonparametric statistics on dense image time series. Using VSIs derived from Sentinel-2 10m EVI2 time series, we have compared the seasonal maxima of weedy crop fields with nearby fields without apparent weediness. The degree of divergence of the weedy VSIs from the non-weedy VSIs depended on crop type and geographic setting. The purpose of this exercise was to provide evaluation of the sensitivity of the VSIs to spectral contributions from non-crop targets. We will be expanding this analysis to all the field data collected during the 2023, 2024, and 2025 campaigns as well as the relevant VSIs derived from the Sentinel-2 data for these years.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported, in part, by NASA Land Cover / Land Use Change (LCLUC) program project 80NSSC23K0535 and, in part, by a grant from the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS – UEFISCDI, project number PN-IV-PCB-RO-MD-2024-0511, within PNCDI IV. We gratefully acknowledge the logistical assistance to the field campaigns in 2023, 2024, and 2025 provided by the Ovidius University of Constanța.

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